
How the Pharmaceutical Industry Expands Diagnoses and Promotes Diseases (Disease Mongering)

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Note: This science communication piece is based on the article “*Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the Pharmaceutical Sector*” [1], authored by the same researcher, and derives from the doctoral dissertation “*The Consolidation of the Pharmaceutical Sector in the Global Economy: Growth, Influence, Deviations, and Marketing*” [2].

The Global Rise of the Pharmaceutical Industry

Over the last century, since Alexander Fleming’s discovery of penicillin in 1928, the pharmaceutical sector has undergone profound productive, organizational, and political transformations [2]. Companies that were initially small—often family-run and restricted to local markets [3]—gave way to large multinational corporations valued at hundreds of billions of dollars [4], with global reach [5] and growing influence over scientific agendas, clinical practices, and regulatory arenas [1, 2, 5].

This process of expansion resulted from the combination of scientific and technological advances—such as the development of new medicines [6, 7, 8]—and broader socioeconomic transformations, including accelerated urbanization, industrial growth, mass production, rising per capita income, expanded access to health systems, and higher levels of education [9, 10]. Together, these factors increased demand for pharmaceuticals and consolidated their centrality as a recurrent response to health problems across diverse social contexts [2].

Beyond these widely recognized drivers, critical scholarship has highlighted the sector’s adoption of controversial practices of corporate influence, synthesized in the article “*Influence, Deviations, and Excesses in the pharmaceutical sector*” [1]. These practices are organized into eight major

analytical categories: (i) lobbying and campaign financing; (ii) influence over regulatory and oversight bodies; (iii) influence in patient organizations; (iv) influence in the drafting of clinical guidelines; (v) manipulation, selective promotion, and concealment of research and drug trials; (vi) ghostwriting; (vii) strategies of diagnostic expansion and disease promotion (disease mongering); and (viii) financing and the provision of benefits to prescribers and institutions, including psychosocial mechanisms and formative dimensions.

Rather than isolated practices, these mechanisms operate structurally and institutionally, producing cumulative effects on public policies, regulatory processes, the production and circulation of scientific evidence, clinical guidelines, and therapeutic decision-making.

This report focuses specifically on category (vii): strategies of diagnostic expansion and disease promotion (disease mongering). Drawing on empirical evidence and case studies, it examines – concisely and accessibly – how these mechanisms operate and their implications for clinical practice and contemporary health systems.

Strategies of Diagnostic Expansion and Disease Promotion (Disease Mongering)

For decades, pharmaceutical companies have been accused of “creating diseases” to expand markets and increase medication sales [11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. This phenomenon, known as disease mongering, broadly consists of expanding diagnostic boundaries in order to increase the number of individuals considered eligible for treatment. In some cases, medications are promoted for natural or everyday conditions that do not necessarily require pharmacological intervention, shifting attention toward the profitability of chemical treatment.

As Tiefer (2006) observes, each condition that becomes the object of such tactics has its own particular history [15]. An emblematic example emerged in the late 1980s and early 1990s, when Pfizer researchers were investigating sildenafil as a treatment for angina, a type of chest pain associated with heart disease. During clinical trials, the compound proved ineffective for the originally proposed indication; however, researchers and participants observed an unexpected side effect: increased erections [16]. From this unexpected outcome emerged Viagra, which would become one of the most commercially successful medications in contemporary history.

Anticipating substantial sales, Pfizer developed a wide-reaching advertising strategy. A key decision was the recruitment of former U.S. Senator and presidential candidate Robert Dole as spokesperson. Dole had publicly disclosed his experience with erectile dysfunction following prostate cancer surgery [17]. Following commercial success, advertising campaigns initially directed at older men or those with medical conditions affecting sexual performance were expanded to target younger men interested in enhancing sexual performance [18].

The campaign also incorporated sports celebrities. Among them was baseball player Rafael Palmeiro, then 37 years old and playing for the Texas Rangers (2002), who appeared in commercials presenting himself as a user of the drug (*figure 1*) and associating it with culturally constructed notions of masculinity and virility linked to baseball [19]. In 2002, Pfizer began sponsoring Major League Baseball (MLB), one of the principal professional sports leagues in the United States [20]. In 2005, it renewed and expanded this sponsorship by funding the “*Major League Baseball Comeback Player of the Year Award, presented by Viagra (sildenafil citrate)*” [21].

In Brazil, a similar visibility strategy mobilized nationally recognized icons. Former football player Pelé (Edson Arantes do Nascimento), three-time FIFA World Cup champion with the Brazilian national team, was hired as a spokesperson for Viagra (*annex 3 of the article*). In 2003, Pelé addressed the 58th Congress of the Brazilian Society of Cardiology, speaking about stigmas associated with erectile dysfunction and emphasizing the importance of discussing the condition [22].

An analysis of Pfizer's promotional materials by Lexchin (2006) identified a recurring pattern: while the company sought to raise public awareness of erectile dysfunction, it largely neglected the emotional and socioeconomic dimensions associated with the condition, concentrating treatment solutions almost exclusively on medication use [16]. Company materials claimed that more than half of men over 40 experienced difficulty achieving or maintaining an erection. Simultaneously, the company suggested that medication was appropriate even for infrequent episodes, while employing images of young and virile men in its campaigns [16].

Commercial results were substantial. Between 1999 and 2017, Viagra generated more than US\$1 billion in annual revenue each year, totaling approximately US\$35 billion for Pfizer since its launch [23, 24]. Today, the global erectile dysfunction drug market is valued at approximately US\$2.30 billion annually [25], with multiple companies competing through similar products or generic versions following the expiration of Viagra's patent.

The drug's success also stimulated expansion beyond male consumers. As Hartley (2006) argues, pharmaceutical companies sought to create a female sexual condition analogous to male erectile dysfunction in order to broaden the market for sexual medications [26]. During this process, companies organized medical conferences and sponsored specialists to promote media discussions regarding the "need" for pharmacological approval [18]. Although initial compounds tested by companies such as Pfizer and Procter & Gamble showed limited results [15], sustained advocacy culminated in the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approving flibanserin (Addyi) in 2015 and bremelanotide (Vyleesi) in 2019 for the treatment of "hypoactive sexual desire disorder" in women. These approvals generated controversy, including concerns regarding limited evidence of efficacy, disagreements among reviewers, intense lobbying and public relations campaigns, regulatory precedents, and conflicting testimonies from patients and experts [27, 28].

Figure 1. Baseball player Rafael Palmeiro (Texas Rangers), then 37 years old, featured in a 2002 Viagra advertising campaign in which he presented himself as a user of the medication. Source: Brisbee (2014).

Diagnostic expansion extends beyond sexuality. According to Moynihan and Cassels (2006) and Lane (2008), shyness was reframed as pathology under the label of social phobia (or social anxiety), a transformation largely associated with pharmaceutical industry interests [29, 30]. In 1999, following the approval of Paxil (paroxetine) for social phobia, SmithKline Beecham (now GlaxoSmithKline, GSK) launched an aggressive marketing campaign that included direct-to-consumer television and magazine advertising, with investments estimated in the tens of millions of dollars [18].

Nationally broadcast advertisements depicted melancholic individuals accompanied by alarmist messaging. Social phobia was portrayed as both debilitating and widespread (*annex 4 of the article*). Expressions such as “*more than 10 million Americans suffer from social anxiety,*” “*imagine being allergic to people,*” “*do you suffer?,*” “*Paxil offers new hope*”, and “*Paxil helps correct the chemical imbalance associated with this disorder*” encouraged viewers to consider medication use, promising favorable outcomes (*annex 4 of the article*). As discussed in relation to ghostwriting, the company also sponsored physician education programs and financed ghostwritten articles supporting Paxil or discrediting competitors [31]. Subsequently, the company faced lawsuits linking Paxil use to violent behavior and suicidality, particularly among children and adolescents [32].

Another case examined by Moynihan et al. (2002) describes how baldness was framed as a significant health concern in Australia following the approval of finasteride (Propecia) in the late 1990s. Merck launched a media campaign supported by studies and institutes funded by the company, presenting baldness as a serious medical issue associated with emotional distress, panic, and potential employment disadvantages [12].

Industry influence in redefining diseases and expanding “treatable” populations was further identified in a cross-sectional study by Moynihan et al. (2013), which examined national and international guidelines establishing diagnostic criteria for common conditions between 2000 and 2013 [33]. Most guidelines proposed definitional changes that broadened the population considered ill, and none of the panels rigorously evaluated potential harms associated with such expansions. In addition, in most panels more than half of the members reported financial ties to pharmaceutical companies [33].

In psychiatry, concerns appear particularly pronounced. Critics have questioned the centrality of the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) as the principal determinant of psychiatric diagnoses [34, 35, 36, 37, 38]. Recurrent criticisms include the proliferation of classifications [34], insufficient attention to individual and socioeconomic contexts [39], low diagnostic thresholds, and the resulting expansion of populations eligible for mental disorder diagnoses [40].

Published by the American Psychiatric Association (APA), the DSM compiles descriptions and criteria used by health professionals to identify mental disorders. Over six decades, the number of disorders increased significantly – from 106 in DSM-I (1952) to more than 300 in DSM-5 (2013) [41]. Although widely regarded as the “bible of contemporary psychiatry,” successive editions of the DSM emerged from complex processes involving pharmaceutical industry interests, professional groups, patient organizations, insurers, and social movements [42]. Its development and revision, therefore, are not insulated from economic, political, historical, and social influences [42].

Among prominent critics is psychiatrist Allen Frances, former chair of the DSM-IV task force. In self-reflective critiques, Frances has acknowledged limitations in the diagnostic system and raised concerns that pharmaceutical industry interests may have contributed to diagnostic expansion by redefining pathologies and transforming common life experiences into psychiatric disorders, thereby encouraging medication use [34].

Empirical evidence regarding conflicts of interest reinforces these concerns. Cosgrove et al. (2006) found that 56% of the 170 DSM-IV task force members had one or more financial relationships with the pharmaceutical industry, including research funding, consultancies, and paid lectures [43]. In certain committees, such as “Mood Disorders” and “Schizophrenia and Other Psychotic Disorders,” all members reported at least one conflict of interest. Later, Cosgrove and Krimsky (2012) identified a similar pattern in DSM-5: in approximately three-quarters of working groups, most members had financial ties to industry [44]. As in DSM-IV, committees in which pharmacological treatment was considered first-line intervention exhibited the highest rates of conflicts of interest, intensifying concerns about industry influence in defining and disseminating psychiatric diagnoses [44].

Final Considerations

This report has examined strategies of diagnostic expansion and disease promotion (disease mongering) not as isolated events, but as components of a recurring dynamic of therapeutic market expansion. The central argument does not deny the reality of suffering nor the clinical relevance of pharmacological treatment when appropriately indicated. Rather, it highlights how the boundaries of what is socially and clinically defined as “disease” may be shifted, expanding the number of individuals classified as patients and consolidating medication as the preferred therapeutic response – even in cases where ordinary life experiences are reframed through a strictly clinical lens.

The cases analyzed demonstrate that marketing plays a central role in producing and circulating meanings about health and illness. Advertising does not merely promote products; it contributes to constructing the problem itself, naming it, quantifying it, and linking it to standardized therapeutic solutions. In this process, emotional, socioeconomic, and relational dimensions of suffering tend to be marginalized, while a narrative centered on chemical correction and restoration of normative performance and functionality gains prominence. Medicalization may thus advance through subtle mechanisms, including the lowering of diagnostic thresholds, amplification of perceived risks, and the transformation of human variation into treatable deficits.

The issue acquires additional significance given that diagnostic expansion extends beyond individual consumer decisions, generating cumulative effects on clinical practice, guideline development, and health system governance. Expanding diagnostic definitions without rigorous evaluation of potential harms may contribute to overdiagnosis, unnecessary treatment, increased exposure to adverse effects, and misallocation of healthcare resources, with direct consequences for public health priorities.

Ultimately, what is at stake is the social meaning of disease itself: who defines the boundaries between the normal and the pathological, which experiences are recognized as legitimate clinical suffering, and which therapeutic responses become dominant. A critical analysis of disease mongering therefore requires acknowledging the political dimension of diagnosis and examining how clinical criteria, cultural expectations, and economic interests intersect. The contemporary challenge lies in sustaining health practices that recognize genuine suffering without automatically subsuming it under market logic, preserving diagnosis as an instrument of care rather than a mechanism for expanding consumption.

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